

CREEP ANISOTROPY IN SHORT FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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Detailed structural studies on injection mouldings of short fibre reinforced thermoplastics have shown that, in addition to a broad fibre length distribution, the fibre orientation varies in a complex manner through the thickness and from place to place in the moulding. This leads to inhomogeneity and anisotropy of mechanical properties. A comprehensive programme designed to assess the validity of theories for composite stiffness, which may be applied to short fibre reinforced thermoplastics, is being carried out. In the absence of 'ideal' samples, injection moulded samples have been used and quantitative information obtained on fibre orientation distribution and fibre length distribution for these mouldings. This data, together with matrix tensile stiffness data, has been used in the prediction of composite tensile stiffness for glass fibre reinforced polybutylene terephthalate over a wide range of test temperatures. Good agreement is obtained between theory and experiment at low strain using a laminate analogy approach; the properties of a uniaxially aligned ply being calculated using the Halpin-Tsai equations but with an alternative equation for the effect of fibre length on ply tensile stiffness in the fibre alignment direction.

In addition to the above studies of low strain 100 sec. tensile creep modulus, long term creep tests for a range of stress levels have been carried out at several temperatures. At the strain levels encountered in these tests, both matrix and composite exhibit non-linear viscoelastic behaviour. It has been found that reasonable predictions of composite creep behaviour at these finite strains can be made using the above-mentioned theory and matrix creep data selected on an equal 100 second strain' basis.

INTRODUCTION

The stiffness of thermoplastics can be raised significantly by the incorporation of short, stiff fibres such as glass or carbon, despite limitations imposed on fibre length and volume fraction by the desire to process the reinforced materials by normal injection moulding procedures. Unfortunately, detailed structural studies on moulded components have shown that the fibre orientation varies in a complex manner through the thickness and from place to place in the moulding [1,2]. The resulting anisotropy and inhomogeneity of mechanical properties leads to difficulties in the presentation of suitable stiffness design data and the use of this data in design with these short fibre reinforced thermoplastics (SF RTP). Furthermore, compounding of the material and processing by injection moulding leads to a broad distribution of fibre lengths in the moulded components; the fibre lengths (or more strictly, fibre aspect ratios) being in the range in which composite stiffness is very dependent on fibre aspect ratio (i.e. typically in the range from 8:1 to 50:1).

To improve our understanding of these materials, a comprehensive programme designed to assess the validity of composite theories which may be applied to SF RTP is being carried out. Ideally, samples in which the fibres were all of one length, perfectly uniaxially aligned and uniformly dispersed in the thermoplastic matrix would have been preferred in the initial studies. Unfortunately it is not possible to prepare such samples in the fibre length range of interest (0.1 mm to 1 mm for glass fibres of 10 μ diameter) and samples produced by injection moulding have had to be used throughout the programme. This was made possible by the successful application of the technique of contact micro-radiography (CMR) to the quantitative determination of the complex fibre orientation distribution (FOD) in the moulded samples [1,3]. This FOD data, together with data on fibre length, fibre fraction, fibre stiffness and stiffness data on the thermoplastic matrix has been used with simple theories for the prediction of composite stiffness in uniaxial tension [4], flexure [5] and simple shear [6]. The predictions have been compared with experimental data for all three modes of deformation using specimens from a variety of bar and plaque injection mouldings in a range of short glass fibre reinforced thermoplastics. Encouraging agreement between theory and experiment was obtained in all cases.

The initial studies in each deformation mode were carried out at room temperature and were restricted to short term stiffness at low strains, where the behaviour of the thermoplastic matrix and the composite could be regarded as linear viscoelastic. The studies in uniaxial tension were subsequently extended to cover a range of test temperatures in order to test the validity of the simple theories over a wider range of conditions. Although reasonable agreement between theory and experiment was still obtained, the results suggested that agreement between theory and experiment over a very limited range of test conditions near room temperature was in no way sufficient as an assessment of the more general validity of the theory for this class of materials (SF RTP).

The purpose of the present programme was then to extend the studies in uniaxial tension to an examination of the long term creep behaviour both at very low strains (where matrix and composite behaviour could be regarded as linear viscoelastic) and at finite strains (i.e. in the strain range for which both matrix and composite exhibit non-linear viscoelastic behaviour) for a wide range of test temperatures.

The glass transition of the thermoplastic matrix used was such that creep tests could be readily carried out below, in and above the glass transition region.

In addition, detailed studies were carried out on the composite at two levels of fibre concentration and the characterisation of the fibre orientation distributions was refined.

These extensions now permit a more critical evaluation of the theories than was possible hitherto.

THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

For continuous, uniaxially aligned fibres, a rule of mixtures based on a parallel model has been found to agree well with experimental values for the tensile modulus of specimens tested in the direction of fibre alignment. The Young's modulus of the composite, E_c , is then given by

$$E_c = E_f V_f + E_m (1-V_f) \quad (1)$$

where E_f and E_m are the Young's moduli of the fibre and matrix respectively and V_f is the fibre volume fraction.

For uniaxially aligned fibres of finite length, Eq.(1) may be modified by the inclusion of a length correction factor, η_L , such that

$$E_c = \eta_L E_f V_f + E_m (1-V_f) \quad (2)$$

Various expressions have been developed for η_L . Cox 7 gives

$$\eta_L = 1 - \frac{\tanh(\beta L/2)}{(\beta L/2)} \quad (3)$$

where L is the fibre length and β is given by

$$\beta = \left[\frac{2\pi G_m}{E_f A_f \ln(R/r_o)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

G_m being the matrix shear modulus, A_f the cross-sectional area of the fibre, r_o the fibre radius and R the mean separation of fibres normal to their length.

To take account of the wide distribution of fibre lengths encountered in SFRTM materials, Eq.(3) may be modified to give

$$\eta_L = \frac{1}{V_f} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n (V_f)_i \left[1 - \frac{\tanh(\beta L_i/2)}{(\beta L_i/2)} \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

Eq. (2) can be further modified to include the case of a distribution of fibre orientations :

$$E_c = \eta_o \eta_L E_f V_f + E_m (1-V_f) \quad (5)$$

For the general case of a planar fibre orientation distribution, Krenchel [8] proposed that η_o be given by the simple form

$$\eta_o = \sum_{k=1}^m a_k \cos^4 \theta_k \quad (6)$$

where a_k is the fibre fraction at the orientation angle θ_k to a reference axis (chosen to be in the direction of measurement of E_c) and m is the number of angle intervals into which the fibre orientation distribution is divided.

Reasonably accurate predictions of composite tensile stiffness have been made using Eq.(5) and (6) for tests carried out in the direction of predominant fibre alignment or for tests on samples in which the fibre orientation

distribution approximates to random-in-the-plane [4]. However, it is apparent that these simple equations predict that fibres lying transverse to the direction of applied stress offer no reinforcement to the matrix and it has been shown that the Krenchel theory becomes significantly inferior to more rigorous treatments when composites containing reasonably well aligned short fibres are tested transverse to the predominant fibre alignment direction [6].

A more rigorous analysis of the effects of fibre orientation on composite stiffness was proposed by Halpin et. al. [9]. This is based on a theory for predicting the stiffness of a laminate consisting of a number of individual plies, each containing matrix and uniaxially aligned fibres, with the fibres of each ply aligned in a different direction. For each ply, the tensile moduli parallel, E_{11}^P , and transverse,

E_{22}^P , to the fibre alignment direction, the shear modulus G_{12}^P and the Poisson's ratio ν_{12}^P are required. The stiffness coefficients for the ply, C_{ij}^P , are calculated from these quantities. Standard transformation equations are then used to calculate the stiffness coefficients of each ply in a chosen set of coordinate axes. The stiffness coefficients for the laminate in this coordinate system, C_{ij}^L , are then obtained by summing the transformed ply stiffnesses through the total thickness of the laminate; each ply stiffness being weighted according to the fraction of the total laminate thickness it occupies. E_{11}^L, E_{22}^L etc. for the laminate in the chosen coordinate system can be readily calculated from the C_{ij}^L .

Halpin et. al. proposed the use of the 'Halpin-Tsai' equations for the calculation of E_{11}^P etc. for each ply [10]. The fibres in the ply may be continuous or discontinuous, but only E_{11}^P is a function of fibre aspect ratio.

Halpin et. al. further proposed that short-fibre reinforced plastics composites (with planar FOD) could be modelled mathematically as laminated systems. This requires quantitative information on the total through-thickness FOD in the composite. The thickness of a 'ply', taken to be aligned at angle θ_k to a reference axis in the plane of the sheet, is proportional to the fibre fraction, a_k , at the angle θ_k in the total through-thickness FOD. The composite stiffness is then calculated by summing the stiffness of these 'plies' using the procedures established in the basic laminate theory. Details of this 'laminate analogy' approach may be found elsewhere [11, 12].

The Halpin-Tsai equations have been used with the laminate analogy in the present programme. The predictions from this approach will be referred to by the abbreviation H-T/L.A. below. Details of the particular Halpin-Tsai equations used are given in equations 1 to 6 of reference [10]. The equation for E_{11}^P for a ply was extended to accommodate the wide distribution of fibre lengths encountered with the materials used in this study.

In the above H-T/L.A. approach, only E_{11}^P depends on fibre aspect ratio. It is therefore possible to examine and compare theories for the dependence of E_{11}^P on aspect ratio by replacing the H-T equation for E_{11}^P with other relations for E_{11}^P . Two such relations have been used below.

Firstly, the relation due to Cox, given in Eq.(2) and (4) above has been used. This will be referred to as the Cox/L.A. approach below.

Secondly, a relation given by Ogorkiewicz and Weidmann [13] has been used after modification to allow for summation over the fibre length distribution. (For details see Eq.(3) of reference 13). The relation is based on the work of Counto [14]. It will be referred to as the OWC/L.A. approach below.

EXPERIMENTAL

The materials used in the present study, and their abbreviations used in the text are as follows :

PBT	Poly(butylene terephthalate). Akzo Plastics, Arnite T06 200.
GFPBT/20	PBT containing $(20.0 \pm 0.05)\%$ by weight of well coupled, short glass fibres. Akzo Plastics, Arnite TV6 240.
GFPBT/35	PBT containing $(35.9 \pm 0.05)\%$ by weight of well coupled, short glass fibres. Akzo Plastics, Arnite TV4 270.

Each material was supplied in the form of injection moulded ISO I tensile bars and 2mm thick, 100 mm square, flash-gated plaques by Akzo Plastics bv. (See Fig.1).

Full structural analyses of the GFPBT mouldings were conducted in terms of the fibre orientation distribution (FOD) in layers through the moulding thickness, the fibre length distribution (FLD), fibre diameter and the fibre volume fraction (V_f), using techniques described elsewhere [1, 3, 4].

For all the GFPBT mouldings, the fibres lay predominantly in planes parallel to the top and bottom surfaces of the mouldings. The projected FOD's in these planes are therefore good approximations to the overall three-dimensional FOD's. However, in the present studies, CMR examination of slices cut from the mouldings with their plane perpendicular to the plane of the moulding has been used to estimate the fraction of fibres which are aligned at various angles to the plane of the mouldings. The effect of this out-of-plane FOD on ply stiffness has then been calculated for each 'ply' prior to transforming ply stiffnesses and summing. In most cases the difference in the calculated values of E_{11}^I and E_{22}^I for the laminate, when either the projected FOD in the plane or the full 3-D FOD is used, is very small. Examples of the effect of these differences on the Krenchel factor, η_0 , are given in Table 1. (It should be noted that η_0 does not provide a unique characterisation of the FOD).

Details of the FLD and the planar FOD in layers through the thickness of the GFPBT/20 plaque moulding may be found elsewhere [6].

Some variation in fibre diameter was noted in the mouldings. Examination of some 200 fibres from several different samples gave a mean fibre diameter of 13.6μ ; all fibres examined lying between 12.9μ and 14.1μ .

Tensile creep tests were carried out on specimens cut from the mouldings, as shown in Fig. 1. The tests were conducted on well proven apparatus described previously [15]. In all tests, the temperature of the specimen was controlled to $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The 100 sec. creep modulus data were produced using the procedures defined in British Standard 4618 for the production of 100 second isochronous stress-strain curves [16].

Throughout the programme great care was taken to eliminate differences in measured moduli of the various samples due to differences in storage history between moulding and testing. For all of the long term creep tests at temperatures above 23°C , the specimens were held at the test temperature for 18 hours prior to application of the creep load. This time was reduced to 2 hours for the 100 sec. tests over a range of temperatures.

Figure 1. Injection moulded flash-gated plaque and ISO I tensile bar showing sites from which creep specimens were machined.

COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND PREDICTED 100 SECOND MODULI

The variation of 100 second tensile creep modulus with temperature for 0° and 90° specimens from the plaques is shown in Figs. 2 and 3 for GFPBT/20 and GFPBT/35 respectively. Modulus-temperature data for the ISO I bars of both materials are presented in Fig. 4. The variation of modulus with temperature for both 0° and 90° specimens from a plaque moulded in un-reinforced PBT is included in Fig. 2. The modulus-temperature data for an ISO I bar of PBT showed small differences from the PBT plaque data. Data for the relevant moulding type in PBT is therefore used in the composite predictions referred to below.

Comparison of Figs. 2 and 4 and Figs. 3 and 4 shows that, for both fibre reinforced grades, the stiffness of the ISO I tensile bar is greater than that for the 0° direction in the plaque. This mirrors the differences in FOD reflected by the η_0 data of Table 1; a greater proportion of fibres being aligned predominantly along the bar axis than along the 0° direction of the plaque. Nevertheless, the plaques still possess a significant degree of stiffness anisotropy.

Examination of the data in Figs. 2 to 4 shows that the glass transition region of the materials is centred around 35°C (for this 100 sec. creep data.)

All the moduli in Figs. 2 to 4 were calculated from tests in which the 100 second axial creep strain was 0.1%. At this low strain level, the behaviour of all the unreinforced and glass fibre reinforced specimens approximated to linear viscoelastic.

The predicted behaviour presented in Figs. 2 to 4 was determined using the modulus data for the PBT, together with the structural data for the relevant composite specimen, in the three variations of the laminate analogy approach discussed above. In all cases, the full three-dimensional (3-D) FOD was used. The effect on the predicted composite stiffness of allowing for the out-of-plane fibres can be seen from Table 2. Similar trends were noted for the H-T/L,A and Cox/L,A. approaches.

Figure 2. Variation of low strain, 100 second tensile creep modulus with temperature for specimens cut at 0° and 90° from flash-gated plaques of GFPBT/20 and PBT.

Experimental data, for un-reinforced PBT (0° and 90°): \circ

Experimental data for the composites: \bullet

Predictions: ——— OWC/L.A., - · - · - Cox/L.A.

————— H-T/L.A.

Below the glass transition, all three theories give reasonable predictions of composite stiffness, both parallel (0°) and perpendicular (90°) to the direction of predominant fibre alignment, and no one theory for the effect of fibre length on composite stiffness emerges as clearly superior.

Above the glass transition significant differences between experiment and theory develop, particularly for the (H-T/L.A.) approach. In all cases, closest agreement between theory and experiment is obtained using the Ogorkiewicz-Weidmann equation for E^P in the laminate analogy approach (OWC/L.A.). This agreement is very satisfactory¹¹ at 0° and 90° for the GFPBT/20 plaque and the 90° direction of the GFPBT/35 plaque. However, even the OWC/L.A. approach gives predicted moduli which differ from the experimental composite moduli by

Figure 3. Variation of low strain, 100 second tensile creep modulus with temperature for specimens cut at 0° and 90° from flash-gated plaques of GFPBT/35. (Symbols as for Fig. 2.)

Figure 4. Variation of low strain, 100 second tensile creep modulus with temperature for specimens machined from ISO I bars of GFPBT/20 and GFPBT/35. (Symbols as for Fig. 2.)

Material Sample		V_F	Krenchel Factor, η_o	
			2-D	3-D
GFPBT/20	Plaque (0°)	0.115	0.60	0.58
	ISO I bar	0.115	0.67	0.64
GFPBT/35	Plaque (0°)	0.223	0.62	0.57
	ISO I bar	0.223	0.76	0.66

Table 1. Values of the Krenchel orientation factor, η_o , for the projected FOD in the plane of the moulding (2-D) and the full three-dimensional FOD (3-D) obtained by allowing for the out-of-plane component of the FOD.

Material Specimen		100 Sec. Creep Modulus (GN/m ²)			
		0° C		80° C	
		2-D	3-D	2-D	3-D
GFPBT/20	ISO I bar	7.08	7.01	2.82	2.75
	Plaque 0°	6.65	6.64	2.43	2.41
	Plaque 90°	4.49	4.55	1.14	1.16
GFPBT/35	ISO I bar	11.58	10.83	4.73	4.27
	Plaque 0°	10.15	10.02	3.84	3.73
	Plaque 90°	6.06	6.23	1.59	1.65

Table 2. Predicted values of composite modulus at 0° C and 80° C obtained using the projected FOD in the plane of the moulding (2-D) and allowing for the out-of-plane FOD (3-D). Modulus values obtained using the OWC/L.A. approach,

22%, 18% and 24% for the 0° specimen of the GFPBT/35 plaque, and the ISO I bars of GFPBT/20 and GFPBT/35 respectively.

The above results serve to emphasise the importance of carrying out experiments and predictions over a range of temperatures when seeking to establish theories for the prediction of stiffness for SFRTCP composites.

It should also be noted that the full fibre length distribution has been used in the above calculations. Use of a mean fibre length for the distribution alters the pattern of agreement between theory and experiment over a range of temperature. For example, for the 0° specimen from the GFPBT/35 plaque, use of a mean fibre length in the OWC/L.A. approach alters the predicted stiffness at temperature < 20° C by less than 2% but lowers the predicted stiffness by a further 10% at 80° C.

An obvious source of error in the above predictions lies in the accuracy of the fibre orientation distributions. The following exercise was therefore carried out in order to give an indication of the effect on predicted composite stiffness of an error in the FOD:

The projected FOD in the plane of the moulding for the ISO I bar of GFPBT/35 was combined with the measured out-of-plane FOD for the ISO I bar of GFPBT/20 and used to calculate the stiffness of the GFPBT/20 bar. This special FOD gave an overall η_o value of 0.72 compared with the measured value for the GFPBT/20 bar of 0.64 : a difference which is considered to be rather larger than that due to the possible error in FOD measurement. Calculated values of the stiffness of the bar at 0° C and 80° C for the measured and 'special' FOD's are compared with experimental data in Table 3.

Temp.	Theory	100 Sec. Creep Modulus (GN/m ²)		
		Measured FOD	'Special' FOD	Experiment
0° C	OWC/L.A.	7.0	7.5	
"	Cox/L.A.	6.4	6.8	7.4
"	H-T/L.A.	6.5	6.9	
80° C	OWC/L.A.	2.75	3.05	
"	Cox/L.A.	2.55	2.80	3.3
"	H-T/L.A.	2.05	2.25	

Table 3. Comparison of experimentally measured stiffness values for the GFPBT/20 ISO I bar at 0 C and 80 C with values predicted using the as-measured FOD for the bar and a special FOD (see text for details)

It is apparent that, at 0°C the OWC/L.A. prediction using the 'special' FOD agrees closely with the experimental stiffness of the bar. However, at 80°C, the OWC/L.A. prediction still falls some 8% below the experimentally measured bar stiffness. The H-T/L.A. and Cox/L.A. predictions still do not agree with the experimentally measured stiffness at 0°C. and still fall well below the experimental values at 80°C. Error in FOD measurement alone can not therefore account for the discrepancies between theory and experiment as the test temperature is increased beyond the glass transition.

Examination of figs. 2 to 4 shows that, in most cases, the predicted composite modulus falls below the experimentally measured value. This could suggest that the three fibre length theories used here under-predict the composite stiffness at the shorter fibre lengths (i.e. lower fibre aspect ratios). In this regard, a recent theory due to Laws [17] is worthy of note. An example of the variation of tensile modulus enhancement factor (E_c/E_m) with fibre aspect ratio predicted by Laws and the three theories used here is presented in Fig.5. It is apparent that Laws' theory predicts a higher enhancement factor than the other theories over the entire fibre aspect ratio range of interest for SFRTM materials. The data in Fig.5 are for a composite in which all the fibres are of one length and uniaxially aligned in the direction of test. The application of Laws' theory to the materials studied here, in which there is a distribution of fibre lengths and orientations, is currently under investigation.

COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND PREDICTED LONG TERM CREEP BEHAVIOUR

The comparisons in the preceding section were carried out using data obtained from 100 second creep tests at very low strain, where both the matrix and the composite could be regarded as linear viscoelastic.

As a first extension of this study, the long term creep data obtained at finite strains have been extrapolated to very low strains and experimental creep moduli for the matrix and composite determined for the 'linear viscoelastic region'. At each creep time of interest, the matrix modulus has then been inserted into the theories to give the predicted composite modulus for the same creep time. An example of such an exercise is given in Figure 6 for the 0° and 90° directions of the GFPBT/35 plaque at 23°C. Very good agreement of predicted and experimental creep curve shape is apparent. Similar good agreement has been obtained previously for tensile bars of short glass fibre reinforced polypropylene [18].

Experimental creep data at finite strains, for two stress levels, are given in Figs 7 and 8 for the 0° and 90° directions respectively of the GFPBT/35 plaques at 23°C. At these finite strain levels, both the composite and the matrix exhibit non-linear viscoelastic behaviour and the choice of matrix creep data on which to base the matrix creep modulus for use in the prediction of a composite creep curve at a particular stress level is by no means obvious. The following approach has

Figure 6. Variation of experimental and predicted tensile creep modulus with log (time) for a 0° specimen from the GFPBT/35 plaque. Test temperature 23°C.

- Experimental data (obtained by extrapolation to infinitesimal strains - the error bars indicate the possible errors resulting from this extrapolation).
- Predicted data :
- OWC/L.A., ——— H-T/L.A., -.-.- Cox/L.A.
- (All predictions based on matrix creep data extrapolated to infinitesimal strain).

At high strains the predicted and experimental creep curves diverge with increasing creep time and the predicted stress levels are in general significantly higher than the experimental values. The errors are particularly large for the 90° plaque specimen (Fig.8). However it must be remembered that, in design with these SFRIP materials, the strain will normally be limited to ~ 1%. Below this strain level, the errors in the predicted data could drop to an acceptable level. Further calculations are in progress to examine this possibility.

Experimental creep data at finite strains, for two stress levels, are given in Figs. 9 and 10 for ISO I bars of GFPBT/20 and GFPBT/35 respectively at 30°C and in Fig.11 for 90° specimens from the GFPBT/20 plaque at 50°C. Predicted creep curves and their associated stress levels, obtained using the procedures outlined above, are included in each Figure.

At low strain, good agreement is obtained in all three cases between predicted and experimental creep curve shape, and the associated stress levels. The OWC/L.A. approach is particularly useful.

At high strain, good agreement between theory and experiment is again obtained, particularly for the OWC/L.A. approach.

It is apparent that the material is creeping into the transition at 23°C, through the transition at 30°C and out of the transition at 50°C.

Figure 7. Variation of tensile creep strain with log time for 0° specimens from the GFPBT/35 plaque. Test temperatures 23°C .
 Experimental data: ●
 Predicted data: --- OWC/L.A., — H-T/L.A., - - - Cox/L.A.
 The label for each curve is the associated stress level in MN/m^2 .

Figure 8. Variation of tensile creep strain with log time for 90° specimens from the GFPBT/35 plaque. Test temperature 23°C . (Symbols as for Fig.7).

Figure 9. Variation of tensile creep strain with log time for GFPBT/20 ISO I bar specimens at 30°C. (Symbols as for Fig.7).

Figure 10. Variation of tensile creep strain with log time for GFPBT/35 ISO I bar specimens at 30°C. (Symbols as for Fig.7).

Figure 11. Variation of tensile creep strain with log time for 90° specimens from GFPBT/20 plaques. Test temperature 50°C. (Symbols as for Fig.7).

CONCLUSIONS

The fibre orientation distribution in injection mouldings of short fibre reinforced thermoplastics is complex but techniques are now available which permit quantitative assessment of this FOD. This information on FOD can be obtained in a form suitable for use in the laminate analogy approach to the prediction of composite stiffness, proposed by Halpin and co-workers.

At very low strains, the behaviour of the PBT and GFPBT materials used in this study approximated to linear viscoelastic. In this region, use of the Halpin-Tsai equations for the prediction of stiffness of plies containing uniaxially aligned short fibres, in conjunction with the laminate analogy approach gave good predictions of composite stiffness below the glass transition region for the GFPBT materials used in this study. However, above the glass transition, the predictions of composite stiffness were significantly lower than the experimental values. Closest agreement between theory and experiment was obtained by replacing the equation for E^P in the Halpin-Tsai equations by an equation due to Ogorkiewicz¹¹ and Wiedmann (i.e. the OWC/L.A. approach).

Reasonably accurate predictions of composite creep behaviour at finite strains (where matrix and composite exhibit non-linear viscoelastic behaviour) can be made using the OWC/L.A. approach and matrix creep data obtained at 'equal 100 second strain' to the composite; provided the composite strain is kept below 1%.

This study serves to highlight the importance of using a wide range of test conditions when attempting to assess the validity of a theory for the stiffness of SFRTTP materials. It is also concluded that it is preferable to use quantitative data on fibre length distribution, rather than a mean fibre length, in the predictions of composite stiffness.

The understanding gained from the above studies is being applied to the development of procedures for the generation of composite creep design data, using a minimum of stiffness data on the composite, and to the use of this data in design with SF RTP materials[18].

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